

WORKING ON SUBORDINATE WORD RELATIONSHIPS WHEN STUDYING THE TOPIC OF "PREPOSITION"

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Annotation. The article examines the heterogeneous nature of syntactic relations in a sentence. Their dependence on syntactic functions, on lexical and grammatical features of a word, on syntactic positions of connecting word forms is substantiated.

The ways of practical mastering by students of subordinate syntactic relations, models according to which phrases are created, taking into account the choice and use of prepositions, are determined. The importance of prepositional control is proved by defining the functions of prepositions, distinguishing their syntactic meanings

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In a sentence taken separately or included in any segment of coherent speech, in the text, word forms appear in syntactic connections and relationships that organize the sentence into an integral unit of communication. However, the syntactic connections in the sentence are heterogeneous. Some of these connections come directly from the word as a lexical and grammatical unit, are predetermined by it and do not depend on the syntactic functions that this word performs in a sentence; other connections arise in a sentence and are conditioned by the syntactic positions of the connecting word forms. So, in the sentence *Under a blizzard that sweeps overhead, Under a downpour, over a humming plain, I will not leave my post, like a sentry Posted by a sleepless divorcee* (Vanshenkin), several types of connections are presented

These are, firstly, connections in such combinations as *buzzing over the plain, sweeps over my head, (I will not) leave my post, a sleepless divorcer*; secondly, the connection of the subject with the predicate (*I will not leave my post*); thirdly, the connection of the name in the form of the creative case with the meaning of the acting the subject (breeding) with the passive participle; fourthly, the connection of circumstantially significant word forms with all the rest of the composition of the proposal they define; *Under a blizzard, under a*

downpour - I will not leave my post. In the first case, we have a connection predetermined by the word, regardless of its role and place in the sentence: in all its forms, in any syntactic positions or taken in isolation, the verb to hum can have a defining form over what (to hum over the plain, over the forest, over the sea ...), the verb to descend - its defining form from what (to leave the post, from the ship, from the stage ...), the noun breeding is an agreed definition (sleepless, vigilant, breeding)

Such a syntactic connection, realized in a sentence, but predetermined not by the syntactic position of the word, but by the word itself, is called a verbal subordinate connection. On the basis of subordinate relations of words in the language system, phrases are constructed. N. Y. Shvedova reveals this concept in this way: "... subordinate connection of words is a formal grammatical dependence of one word on another, in which the presence of a dependent word in a certain form is predetermined by the categorical properties of the dominant word" [4, p.486].

Therefore, it is important for students to theoretically and practically master subordinate syntactic relations, the models by which phrases are created in order to master the language. It is clearly not enough to study phrases in syntax, since only in morphology the categorical properties of the words included in the phrases are most deeply and fully illuminated. Studying them in isolation from syntax, from speech activity, would lead to mechanical, aimless work for students. Morphology will provide great opportunities for improving the syntactic structure of students' speech, and of the morphological topics, the preposition is especially interesting because of its "syntacticism", since the forms of prepositional control play a big role in the language. V. V. Vinogradov believes that it is "in the rules of combining words through prepositions that the national specificity of the language is clearly manifested" [1, p.232].

A. H. Vostokov paid great attention to prepositional phrases. It clearly distinguishes the types of syntactic meanings and the functions of prepositions. The latter result from their lexical meanings, which are conditioned by connections with words of certain semantic categories. The researcher also points out that prepositions can serve as a means of control for certain limited semantic categories of words (to be angry at someone, something, etc.), or they may turn out to be "frozen" as part of a particular grammatical turnover (to be born into a father, go out into the world, believe in fate, etc. etc.). Highlighting different types of grammatically related or formal, auxiliary use of prepositions, A. H. Vostokov distinguishes them in connection with the analysis of the

corresponding types of phrases. For example, phrases with the preposition for in the creative case of a noun indicate the question where?, speaking of an object that obscures or separates something from another: being behind; for example: Behind a house, behind a fence, over the mountains, over the sea. Speaking of the limits within which someone is imprisoned – being outside; for example: Outside the city, abroad, beyond the line [2, p. 180].

It should be borne in mind that in the Russian language, along with formal, "empty" prepositions (longing for a daughter, dreaming of the future, living in the city, etc.), serving only to express syntactic connections, there are prepositions and prepositional combinations that have retained a clear individuality of their lexical meaning (for the reason, thanks, glory, in the name, next to, etc.).

Prepositions form rich synonymous series, the members of which can be contrasted by a subtle shade in meaning, by stylistic affiliation, by compatibility with other words. So, in the synonymous series from, for, because of, by, under, thanks to, due to, in view of, as a result of, for, in connection with, expressing causal relations, prepositions from and due to differ in shades of meaning (negative and positive reason), and prepositions from and as a result of stylistic belonging and compatibility with other words. Like synonyms of any part of speech, they need to be studied at least in a minimal context (i.e. in a phrase). "The complex and nuanced synonymy of prepositions", the ability to enter into antonymic relations require the study of this part of speech in lexico-semantic terms [3, p.540].

Thus, only the simultaneous study of the preposition in the natural connections of the language system (lexico-semantic, stylistic, morphological and syntactic) will help the teacher enrich the syntax of students' speech

The interrelation of different aspects of the consideration of a preposition, the theoretical complexity of constructing a methodology, the erasure of the lexical meanings of individual prepositions with the vivid lexical individuality of others, the variety of syntactic relations expressed by prepositions, the small number of hours devoted to this topic leads to the fact that the teacher does not improve the syntactic structure of students' speech. When using prepositions in speech, students do not know how to choose a preposition in accordance with the semantic connections between words (for example: we cleared the area for the rink, instead of for the rink); they often do not feel the shades in the meaning of synonymous prepositions, they do not know how to select the preposition

that will help accurately express the thought and corresponds to the style of speech. Here are some examples

The most typical and persistent mistake is the confusion of prepositions with and from expressing spatial relations: "returned from Belarus", "from Sokolniki", "from the Far East". There is mainly an illegal substitution of the preposition from preposition C. There are isolated errors in mixing prepositions through and through: "*A fluffy cat sneaked into the next house through the window.*"

Using in sentences such as "*My head hurt because of the intense heat*", "*Woke up because of strong sounds*", the preposition because, instead of the more appropriate from, students seem inclined to emphasize the undesirability of the cause. It is completely inappropriate to use the preposition from instead of because in the sentence "*We did not go to the museum for lack of time.*" Mistakes are made in the inappropriate use of prepositions due to, thanks to: "*Our fields are covered with juicy greens due to the past rains*", "*I got a deuce due to illness*". Students do not know that the preposition because of expresses an undesirable reason, and because of – a positive one

A preposition such as in connection with is rarely used to express causal relations, and not all students know which case it requires ("I could not complete the task due to illness"). Many students do not feel the style of speech. For example, the use of a sentence like "In the summer they go to the forest for mushrooms, berries and cranberries in the forest" with the obviously colloquial use of the preposition by instead of the literary for (in the meaning of the goal).

The analysis of the features of the use of prepositional constructions by students in speech shows the urgent need to improve the skills of using prepositions and expressing subordinate relations with their help. The selection of proposed grammatical structures for study can be determined by the following criteria: 1) their prevalence in the modern literary language; 2) the lack of active stock of students; 3) difficulties associated with their use (the presence of speech errors).

Prepositional verb phrases with nouns are very common in modern literary speech. They are diverse in the nature of the relationships they express. Phrases consisting of a verb and a noun, expressing spatial and temporal relationships, are widely used by students in speech. The teacher's task is to work on the synonymy of prepositions expressing this kind of syntactic relations. It is also necessary to work on subordinate syntactic relations that have causal significance. Verb phrases with some prepositions with causal

meaning are very productive. Adjectival phrases with the preposition from (pale from fright) are also widely used in the language. It is important to enrich the syntax of students' speech and phrases expressing target relationships (to work for victory).

It seems that such work should be systematically combined with work on grammatical features and spelling of the preposition. Types of exercises, didactic material, examples, teacher's comments – everything needs to be subordinated to this goal. Here are the exercises, distributing the material according to the types of relations expressed by prepositional constructions, and correlating it with the topics studied in the program

Spatial relations are subtly differentiated in language; they assume three dimensions: length, width, height (depth). All non-derivative prepositions, with a few exceptions, together with the case forms of names, are expressions of spatial relations. Students use many of them freely and unmistakably in speech. Therefore, the work on these prepositions can be complicated by the selection of synonyms and antonyms for them

Task. Match the selected prepositions expressing spatial relations with synonyms. How do they differ from each other? Remember their spelling.

1. **Около** дома, возле крылечка, тихо течет безымянная речка. 2. У крыльца, **возле** нашего дома, лужа, полная звезд. 3. **Вблизи** края воды вдруг шевельнулся один из прелых листков, потом вылезла водяная крыса. 4. Сообразив в одно мгновение, что это лось, Петя пустился по боковой протоке **навстречу** ему.

One of the synonymous series (prepositions *okolo*, *podle*, *vozle*) indicates immediate proximity, the preposition *near* (something) is a more distant object. All of them are synonymous with the primitive prepositions *u*, *pri*, but differ in their ability to combine with different words: *near the sea* – *by the sea*, but the combination *near the mother* cannot be replaced by the combination *at the mother*, since another meaning arises. Working on antonyms can be used as a means to better understand the meaning of prepositions.

Task. Name the phrases in which prepositions express spatial relationships. Find antonymous prepositions. Prove the correctness of your answer

1. Успокоился май озорной, белым цветом усыпал дороги, то роняет звезду над тобой, то ромашки бросает под ноги. 2. Хорошо бродить весной непрямую травую от березки до осинки, от росинки до росинки,

от качнувшейся ромашки до медвяной белой каши. 3. Сегодня курсом в Антарктиду ушли из порта корабли

Sample comments from the teacher. The prepositions under – over, from – to, from – to, from – to, from – to in these sentences have spatial meaning and are antonyms.

Under – over. The preposition over indicates the position of the object at the top of something, and under - at the bottom, i.e. prepositions are words with the opposite meaning (cf. adverbs–antonyms: up - down, nouns–antonyms: top - bottom).

Prepositions from and to are antonyms, since the preposition from means that the object named by the noun is the starting point of movement (to wander from where?), and the preposition to with the genitive case of names denotes the final point of movement, the limit (to wander to what place?).

Prepositions from and to are antonyms. The preposition from serves to indicate the starting point of the movement (the name with this preposition answers the question from where?), and the preposition to indicates the opposite direction of movement, the final point (where?): from Brazil to Brazil.

Prepositions with and on are antonyms (the explanation is about the same). It is necessary that students learn the prepositions-antonyms from and to, on and with well, since they often use them incorrectly in speech. Relying on their meaning (entered the house (inside) – left the house; climbed on the roof (on the surface) – got off the roof) does not always give results. With geographical names, institutions, and territories, their use is supported by tradition (to the Caucasus, but to the Crimea). If the preposition is used in (went where? – to the Crimea), then only his antonym from (returned from where? – from Crimea). The preposition on is antonymous to the preposition with (went where? – did you return to the Caucasus from where? – from the Caucasus)

Unlike ancient prepositions, derived prepositions are lexically much more independent, and therefore the semantic shades expressed by them are more specific. The spatial functions of adverbial prepositions are emphasized by the lexical, material meaning of the very basis. Therefore, it is not difficult for students to select synonyms and antonyms for them: on top of (something) synonymously above (something); in front of (something) antonymously behind (something). The temporal meanings of prepositions are obviously more recent and develop from spatial ones, according to academician V. V. Vinogradov. The relationships they express are less diverse.

Prepositions used to express causal relationships are numerous in the Russian language. They differ in shades of meaning and stylistic affiliation. Students, using these prepositions in speech, sometimes do not distinguish shades in their meaning, belonging to the style of speech. Hence the shortcomings in use. The tasks of the teacher are: 1) to prevent and correct errors in the use of the most common prepositions; 2) to enrich the syntactic structure of students' speech with such prepositions as in view, in connection with.

The rich synonymy of prepositions with causal meaning implies a lot of work on its development. Prepositions from, under, to, for, because of are common, they are almost devoid of lexical meaning, convey only causal relationships. The most common preposition is from. They are used much less frequently for, for, under, and in most cases it is impossible to replace them with synonymous ones. The preposition has the additional meaning of a reason, a reason (by order, by advice, by approval).

Understanding the subordinate syntactic relations expressed with the help of prepositions, knowledge of shades in their meaning and stylistic affiliation, attention to the lexical meaning of the main and dependent word in a phrase, well-selected didactic material - all this is the key to the correct use of prepositions and prepositional combinations in speech.

Literature:

1. Vinogradov V. V. Questions of studying phrases (based on the material of the Russian language): Selected works. Research on Russian grammar. – Moscow: Nauka Publishing House, 1975.
2. Vinogradov V. V. From the history of Russian syntax. – M.: Publishing House of Moscow University, 1958. – Access mode: <https://danefae.org/lib/vvv/synt/>
3. Vinogradov V. V. Russian language (Grammatical teaching about the word) – 4th ed. – Moscow: Russian language, 2001.
4. Grammar of the modern Russian literary language. – M., Nauka, 1970.
5. Popova, E. I. (2023). TECHNIQUES OF SEMANTIZATION OF RUSSIAN VOCABULARY IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AUDIENCE. Academia Science Repository, 4(03), 227-234.
6. Попова, Е. И. (2023). РИТОРИЧЕСКАЯ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯ В ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ПОДГОТОВКЕ УЧИТЕЛЯ. *Gospodarka i Innowacje*, 42, 332-336.
7. Likhachev, S. V., & Popova, E. I. (2024). Folk orthology in the digital environment. *Russian Language Studies*, 22(1), 43-57.

